

High-Resolution Modeling and Validation of the PULSTAR Reactor

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ABSTRACT

Validating and quantifying the uncertainty of high-resolution nuclear reactor models is challenging due to the scarcity of experimental data at the pin level. The PULSTAR 1 MW_{th} pool-type reactor at North Carolina State University is a good platform for supporting future high-resolution validation experiments, although no pin-level experimental data are currently available. In this work, a Monte Carlo model of the PULSTAR reactor was developed with Serpent 2.2 to characterize the current core state and to support such future activities. The model was validated against historical reactivity measurements. The PULSTAR core has undergone multiple fuel shuffles and configuration changes over its operating history, that are tracked by the model to accurately predict the pin-level depletion of each fuel assembly. A series of depletion calculations were performed, from the initial start-up (Core 0) and up to the current configuration (Core 12). The predicted excess reactivity and control-rod worths at the beginning of each core configuration were compared against the available measurements. The results demonstrate good agreement with experimental data, with most discrepancies below 10%. Larger deviations were observed for Core 8, indicating the need for further investigation of the modeling assumptions. The burnup distribution predicted for Core 12 shows a maximum local pin burnup of 11.93 MWd/kgU. The outcomes from this study contribute to the ongoing efforts to design future high-resolution validation experiments and can support the development of upcoming core configurations. Future work will focus on refining the Serpent models and developing corresponding deterministic models.

Keywords: depletion analysis, pin-level modeling, PULSTAR reactor, Serpent, validation

1. INTRODUCTION

Verification, validation, and uncertainty quantification (VVUQ) of computational models are essential for demonstrating credibility in model predictions [1]. VVUQ is challenging for high-fidelity modeling and simulation (M&S) because pin-resolved experimental data are scarce [2]. The PULSTAR 1 MW_{th} pool-type light water reactor at North Carolina State University (NCSU) provides a good platform for future high-resolution validation activities due to its moderate power level and core accessibility. Currently, no pin-level experimental data are available. The reactor first achieved criticality in 1972 with its initial startup configuration, referred to as Core 0. Since then, the core has undergone multiple reconfigurations: fuel shuffling, off-core cool-down, changes in reflector materials (water, graphite, beryllium), gradual introduction of 6 wt% ²³⁵U fuel assemblies, and evolution of ex-core structures. These changes have produced a complex operational history that must be accurately modeled to support current and future analyses. In preparation for future high-resolution validation experiments, a detailed Serpent 2.2 model of the reactor was developed. The complete pin-level depletion history was simulated from the initial Core 0 through the current Core 12. Predicted excess reactivities were compared against historical measurements recorded in standard operating procedures [3]. The pin-power distributions predicted by Serpent were used to perform a burnup analysis for the full fuel inventory.

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2. PULSTAR CORE DESCRIPTION

The PULSTAR core is located under approximately 6 m of demineralized water. It consists of a 6×6 grid lattice with a pitch of [7.71, 8.1] cm. 25 assemblies are loaded in the core, from an inventory of 43 UO_2 fuel assemblies—34 enriched to 4 wt% and 9 to 6 wt% ^{235}U . Three reflector types have been used, water, graphite and beryllium. The core is strongly under-moderated. A typical core configuration features a 5×5 fuel lattice, with reflectors filling the remaining positions. Each fuel assembly contains 25 fuel rods arranged in a 5×5 grid with a pitch of [1.33, 1.54] cm. The rods contain 40 stacked pellets with a total active height of 60.96 cm. The core is mounted on a grid plate above a plenum chamber at the bottom of the pool. Near the core boundary are a graphite thermal column and six beam tubes that can be flooded or voided, both of which can significantly affect core reactivity. Additional support and instrumentation structures surround the core but exert a smaller influence. Four control rods made of silver–indium–cadmium (80–15–5 wt%) provide reactivity control. The rods are inserted into guide channels near the core center: one regulating (R), two safety (S1, S2), and one shim (M). The reactor is cooled by forced downward convection. At full power, the coolant enters the top of the core at 40.6°C , exits at 48.5°C , and the average fuel temperature is 145°C , with a mass flow rate of 31.55 kg/s. A total of 12 core configurations have been used since the reactor’s initial start-up, illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. PULSTAR core layout (Core 0 through 12).

Accurate M&S of the current Core 12 requires accounting for all previous cores to track the irradiation history of each fuel assembly. Most configuration changes were driven by the need to increase excess reactivity. In Figure 1, the 4 wt% fuel assemblies are labeled 02–35, and the 6 wt% assemblies are labeled 40–45. The indexing of the 6×6 core lattice follows a column-row convention, with columns numbered

1-6 and the rows labeled A-F. Core 0 (1972–1977), referred to as the “standard core” in the PULSTAR documentation, included fuel assemblies 02–26 arranged within columns 1-5 and rows A-E, with water serving as the reflector. Core 1 (1977–1979) used the same fuel layout but added graphite reflectors on the column 6. Core 2 was used only for low-power tests and is not considered here. Core 3 (1979–1999) had the longest operation period. The fuel was shuffled to new positions within columns 1-5 and rows B-F, with additional graphite reflectors in row A and column 6. In Core 4 (1999–2005), 5 graphite blocks in row A were replaced with beryllium. Core 5 (2005–2009) introduced five new 4 wt% assemblies (31–35). New graphite reflector were installed along column 1. In Core 6 (2009–2010), the fuel was repositioned within columns 2-6 and rows B-F, while keeping the graphite reflectors in column 1. Core 7 (2010–2011) involved only fuel shuffling. In Core 8 (2011–2016), the remaining graphite reflectors were replaced with beryllium. Cores 9–11 (2016–2022) involved successive fuel shuffles and the gradual addition of 6 wt% ^{235}U fuel assemblies: 43–44 in Core 10, and 42–45 in Core 11. The current Core 12 (2022–present) includes two additional 6 wt% ^{235}U fuel assemblies (40, 41) and a reshuffling. Additional information about these core configurations can be found in [4, 3]. It is important to note that mechanical constraints on the grid plate impose a 180° rotation when assemblies move between columns 1, 3, 5 and columns 2, 4, 6. Accounting for these rotations is necessary to accurately predict the pin-level burnup.

3. SERPENT MODELS

Serpent models were developed for each core configuration depicted in Figure 2. Serpent is a continuous-energy Monte Carlo reactor physics code developed by VTT that supports steady-state, depletion, and transient calculations [5]. Version 2.2 was used with the JEFF-3.1.1 nuclear data library. Given the number and complexity of the core configurations, manually creating each model would be time-consuming and prone to hard-to-detect errors. To streamline this process, Python scripts were created to read the PULSTAR core parameters such as dimensions and loading pattern, and automatically generate the Serpent inputs. The scripts also enable optional features such as pin- or assembly-level depletion and the flooding or voiding of selected beam tubes. The Serpent reactor models extend beyond the core, radially to the pool tank (≈ 100 cm) and axially about 150 cm. Models of Cores 0 and 12 are shown in Figure 2, where five beam tubes and the thermal column are visible. In Core 0, all beam tubes are flooded, whereas in Core 12, four are voided.

Figure 2. PULSTAR radial geometries for Core 0 and 12 generated by Serpent. The yellow fuel rods have a 4% enrichment, while the red fuel rods have a 6% enrichment.

At the beginning of each core configuration, several calculations are performed to determine the excess reactivity (ρ_E) and the individual control-rod worths for the safety 1 (ρ_1), safety 2 (ρ_2), regulating (ρ_R), and shim (ρ_M) rods. Historical measurements were performed for all these quantities under

Cold, Clean Conditions (CCC). CCC are defined by fuel and coolant temperatures at 21°C and free of ^{135}Xe —typically after three days of reactor shutdown. For each core, the following sequence is executed: (1) excess-reactivity calculation with all rods out (ARO) at CCC; (2) individual control-rod worth evaluations by fully inserting each rod at CCC; (3) depletion at hot, full-power (HFP) conditions with ARO using multiple burnup steps; and (4) zero-power depletion for three days to allow ^{135}Xe decay.

Pin-level depletion is performed using 10 axial nodes per fuel rod, resulting in 6,250 depletion regions. Assembly shuffling and rotations between cores are automated via Python scripts using Serpent's restart capabilities. Each calculation uses 200,000 neutrons per cycle, with 1,000 active and 200 inactive cycles, yielding a k_{eff} statistical uncertainty of 7 pcm. Each core depletion takes approximately 30 hours using one node with 64 CPUs. Memory optimization is necessary to deplete all pins individually. The fission source entropy and peak power were tracked to ensure convergence. Pin-power distributions are tallied at every individual fuel pellet. Post-processing these results across all depletion steps and core configurations provides the pin-level burnup distribution for every fuel assembly.

4. RESULTS

The Serpent predictions for excess reactivity and control-rod worth were compared against historical measurements for all core configurations. Most data were obtained from the PULSTAR Safety Analysis Report [6], with excess reactivity for Cores 8–12 digitized from [3]. The measurements were performed at the beginning of each core configuration under CCC. The discrepancies between predictions and measurements are influenced by the following factors:

1. Epistemic uncertainty due to the measurement process: Excess reactivity is inferred from the difference in control-rod (CR) worth between the critical and all-rods-out (ARO) positions. The CR worth is determined by measuring the reactor period (or doubling time) and applying an estimated one-group delayed neutron decay constant (λ_{eff}), along with an effective delayed neutron fraction (β_{eff}). The uncertainty associated with the reactor period measurement is negligible (≈ 0.3 s, equivalent to about 1 pcm of CR worth). The dominant source of uncertainty arises from assuming a constant β_{eff} value of 730 pcm throughout the reactor lifetime. Serpent calculations indicate that β_{eff} varies by up to 60 pcm between Cores 0 and 12. As an analytical verification, a rough estimate at 4.5 MWd/kg HM shows that $\approx 10\%$ of fissions originate from ^{239}Pu [7], corresponding to a ≈ 45 pcm decrease in the physical delayed neutron fraction. Overall, using a fixed β_{eff} in the measurement process introduces an uncertainty of roughly ± 80 pcm in the CR worth, and consequently in the measured excess reactivity.
2. Modeling assumptions and approximations: The primary approximation in the Serpent model is the use of ARO conditions for depletion calculations. In practice, the reactor operates at criticality with the regulating rod inserted, which affects the neutron flux and pin burnup distribution. Future models will address this approximation and assess its impact.
3. Operational information: Accurate modeling of all core configurations requires detailed operational data spanning more than 50 years, including the flooding or voiding of beam tubes, measurement practices, and potential human factors. The current model relies on assumptions informed by discussions with the NCSU Nuclear Reactor Program, although some historical practices may no longer be recoverable.

Aside from comparing Serpent reactivity predictions with measurements, pin-power distributions were computed and a pin-level burnup analysis was performed for the current reactor state (Core 12).

4.1. Reactivity Calculations

The Serpent models discussed in section 3 were used to predict the reactivities ρ_E , ρ_1 , ρ_2 , ρ_R , and ρ_M . Results for Cores 0-4 are summarized in Table I, for Cores 5-8 in Table II, and for Cores 9-12 in Table III. A good agreement is observed for most core configurations, with discrepancies within 250 pcm for the

majority of reactivity measurements. This corresponds to a mean absolute error of 8%. The main outlier is Core 8, which shows deviations exceeding 20%. It is worth noting, that (a) the energy extracted during Core 8 in 2011 was about three times higher than during the average core life, and (b) the reactivity increased by ≈ 500 pcm mid-cycle. The excess-reactivity discrepancy between the Serpent model and the measured data is therefore likely related to unknown operational conditions. Additionally, these large deviations for Core 8 are also observed in historical PULSTAR reports [4]. A detailed review of these assumptions is planned in coordination with the Nuclear Reactor Program. Another outlier is the shim-rod worth in Core 6, though this rod is no longer in use and therefore has limited relevance.

Table I. Comparison of Serpent reactivity predictions (PRED) against available measurements (MEAS) in pcm for Core 0 (1972) to Core 4 (1999). The prediction statistical uncertainty is at the order of 7 pcm.

	Core 0		Core 1		Core 3		Core 4	
	MEAS	PRED	MEAS	PRED	MEAS	PRED	MEAS	PRED
ρ_1	4165	4345	4084	4061	2655	2759	2943	3079
ρ_2	2631	2716	3185	3029	2267	2126	2502	2285
ρ_R	2521	2601	2379	2478	3982	3793	3664	3583
ρ_M	1644	1708	1899	1908	2961	2815	2696	2630
ρ_E	2047	2286	2102	2445	2890	3097	1588	1658

Table II. Comparison of Serpent reactivity predictions (PRED) against available measurements (MEAS) in pcm for Core 5 (2005) to Core 8 (2011). The prediction statistical uncertainty is at the order of 7 pcm.

	Core 5		Core 6		Core 7		Core 8	
	MEAS	PRED	MEAS	PRED	MEAS	PRED	MEAS	PRED
ρ_1	2348	2630	2583	2437	2246	2451	1991	2685
ρ_2	2961	2954	2808	3069	2695	3018	2246	2789
ρ_R	2787	2896	2757	2787	2634	2883	2297	3062
ρ_M	3727	3252	4492	3586	3982	3642	3522	3283
ρ_E	1991	1909	1901	1737	2839	2614	2969	2896

Table III. Comparison of Serpent reactivity predictions (PRED) against available measurements (MEAS) in pcm for Core 9 (2016) to Core 12 (2022). The prediction statistical uncertainty is at the order of 7 pcm.

	Core 9		Core 10		Core 11		Core 12	
	MEAS	PRED	MEAS	PRED	MEAS	PRED	MEAS	PRED
ρ_1 (pcm)	2850	2802	2500	2606	2550	2483	-	2608
ρ_2 (pcm)	2950	2817	2800	2712	2850	2661	-	2878
ρ_R (pcm)	3000	3086	2900	2994	2900	2961	-	2722
ρ_M (pcm)	-	3234	-	3301	-	3334	-	3078
ρ_E (pcm)	2051	2316	2157	2549	2197	2574	2379	2690

To illustrate the trend across core configurations, Figure 3 plots the discrepancies. Of the 53 measurements, 40 differ by less than 10% (250 pcm) and 49 are within 20% (500 pcm). Only four measurements fall outside these ranges. Considering all the configuration and operational changes over the span of more than 50 years, these results provide confidence in the Serpent models and pin-depletion methodology. This is further reinforced by the fact that the observed deviations are comparable to those reported in historical PULSTAR analyses using the MCNP code for Cores 0–8 [4].

Figure 3. Reactivity prediction discrepancies for each core configuration (a) in pcm, and (b) in %.

4.2. Pin-Power Distributions

Throughout all depletion calculations, tallies were used to obtain the 3D pin-power distribution for each fuel pellet. The axially averaged radial pin-power distributions for the initial Core 0 and Core 12 under HFP ARO conditions are shown in Figure 4a and 4b. A notable shift in the power distribution is observed between these two cores. In Core 0, all fuel assemblies were fresh, leading to higher power in pins adjacent to flooded guide channels due to enhanced moderation. In Core 12, the 4 wt% fuel assemblies are irradiated, and the highest power occurs in the 6 wt% fuel assemblies, which have relatively low burnup since they were introduced in Core 10. Spatially, the power peaking occurs in fuel assemblies located next to both the beryllium reflector and the water gaps around the guide channels.

Figure 4. Radial pin-power distribution for cores 0 and 12 at HFP ARO conditions.

4.3. Burnup Analysis

The pin-power detectors implemented in Serpent across all core configurations were employed to perform a detailed pin-level burnup analysis. The radial burnup distribution of the current core is presented in Figure 5 with both assembly- and pin-resolution. As expected, the 6 wt% fuel assemblies exhibit very low burnup due to their recent introduction. Among the 4 wt% assemblies, the maximum

burnup is 6.6 MWd/kgU at the assembly level and 9.5 MWd/kgU at the pin level. The core-average is 4.2 MWd/kgU. In Figure 6, the key burnup analysis results for the inventory of 4 wt% fuel assemblies are provided.

Figure 5. PULSTAR Core 12 radial burnup distribution.

Figure 6. Burnup analysis results for the inventory of 4% enriched fuel assemblies

Figure 6a shows the pin-resolved burnup in assembly A17, which contains the highest local burnup.

It displays a strong radial gradient, with approximately a factor of 2 between the minimum and maximum. Figure 6b shows assembly A28, the 4 wt% fuel assembly with the lowest local burnup, averaging 4.5 MWd/kgU and exhibiting a smaller gradient. Both A17 and A28 are present in Core 12. Figure 6c compares the axial burnup of the hottest pin in A17 with the assembly-average, highlighting the local maximum of 11.93 MWd/kgU. Figure 6d provides the average burnup of all 4 wt% fuel assemblies, where red denotes those currently in Core 12 and blue indicates those stored. It is worth noting that the average burnup calculated in this study is in good agreement with the PULSTAR annual safety reports. These obtained results can guide future core designs, for instance by replacing the most irradiated assemblies (A02, A10, A17, A26) with lower-burnup stored fuel (A06, A09, A12, A22).

5. CONCLUSIONS

The validation and uncertainty quantification of high-resolution reactor models is very challenging due to lack of pin-resolved experimental data. The PULSTAR reactor at NCSU is well suited for conducting such high-resolution validation activities in the future. In this work, Serpent Monte Carlo models were developed for all 12 PULSTAR core configurations and validated against historical reactivity measurements to support envisioned validation activities. A series of pin-level depletion calculations were performed from the initial start-up Core 0 and up to the current Core 12. Predictions were compared against measurements of excess reactivity and control-rod worths, showing good agreement: most discrepancies were below 10%. Core 8 exhibited larger deviations, likely related to operational assumptions that will require further investigation. The burnup analysis of the current core showed a maximum local burnup of 11.93 MWd/kgU in assembly A17 and provided a per-assembly detailed burnup characterization, which can be used to guide the design of future core layouts. Future work will focus on refining the Serpent models, and developing complementary deterministic models for high-resolution validation and design studies.

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